

convivium
food . living heritage . conviviality

RECIPE Book

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Foreword: CONVIVIALITY

The recipe book in your hands is the result of our first CONVIVIUM team building exercise, launching a three-year research-action project funded by HORIZON Europe under the New European Bauhaus initiative. Rooted in the theme of cultural heritage, CONVIVIUM sets out to explore food as living heritage—a dynamic, evolving practice that both reflects societal change and contributes to the well-being of communities across Europe. More than mere nourishment, food acts as a mirror of shifting identities, shared traditions, diverse social and ecological realities, and the collective futures we are building together. Through teamwork, this cookbook exercise effectively demonstrates that we can leverage our ‘local’ culinary traditions to build new ones, by carrying knowledge, practices, and memories with us, and negotiating their adaptations in new places with differing resources, transcending geographical and cultural divides... North and South, East and West.

Over the course of the project, CONVIVIUM will delve into the varied foodscapes of Europe—those everyday tangible and intangible environments shaped by the production, preparation, and sharing of food. It will examine iconic regional ingredients or products such as wine in southern Europe and salted fish in the north, as well as explore everyday practices in gardens and kitchens. It will engage with community-led initiatives that address food waste, and grapple with broader contemporary themes like migration, urbanization, biodiversity loss, changing tastes (and ecological imperatives), and climate resilience. Through this lens, we aim to understand how food anchors us in tradition while simultaneously inviting us to reimagine heritage in an age of rapid transformation, and to consider ways to give new life to tradition as a future-oriented concept, rather than one rooted in history.

Central to our approach is a deep awareness of the more-than-human world. In response to the legacies of modernity and the pressing ecological crisis, we believe food offers a vital entry point for rethinking how we live, produce, and consume. The choices we make around food—what we grow, how we cook, who we eat with—are intimately linked to how we care for the planet, its diverse inhabitants, both human and other, and for each other. For CONVIVIUM, this is not just a research agenda; it is a call to action.

As part of the project's launch, the University of Coimbra—our coordinating institution—hosted an opening conference where academic and societal partners from across Europe came together. One of the highlights of this gathering was a communal visit to the local market, where, amidst the stalls of fresh produce, spices, and regional specialties, we explored how the fruits of the earth could be reimaged through the lens of our diverse home cultures. Working in teams (selected to pair us with colleagues from differing culinary cultures), we set out to transform local ingredients into dishes reflecting our personal and regional stories, adapted to the setting and available ingredients of our host community. Cooking side by side, learning from one another's culinary traditions, and sharing meals around a common table, we were invited to embody aspects of living heritage.

Heritage is often portrayed as something static or oriented with the past – a set of inherited customs to be preserved unchanged. This project is founded on a different conviction: that Europe's cultures have always been in motion, shaped by migration, trade, adaptation, and exchange. Food, with its universality and immediacy, is perhaps the most accessible and profound way to trace these shifts. The products of the earth nourish more than just our bodies; they shape how we see ourselves, how we relate to our more-than-human others, and how we imagine our place in the world-to-come.

This recipe book may, at first glance, appear to be a somewhat eclectic collection—dishes drawn from various regions and traditions across the continent. Together, they form a compelling snapshot of the richness and diversity of European food cultures, which of course often originate beyond European borders. Each recipe carries its own history, its own memories, its own network of relationships, and its own environmental realities. They are stories written in ingredients and preparation methods, shaped by flows and affect, creativity and intuition, belonging and reinvention. This little book makes up a brief and intuitive culinary journey through contemporary Europe, but also serves as a metaphor for the broader work of CONVIVIUM: the ongoing, collective effort to cultivate connection, creativity, and care for a healthier planet.

In this sense, the cookbook is more than a collection of recipes. It is a seed from which the wider work of the project will grow. The academic research, community events, public workshops, exhibitions, and artistic collaborations stemming from this will build upon this spirit of conviviality—of coming together through food to imagine and enact new forms of belonging. The journey has begun. Let us cook, taste, share, and grow—together.

RICK DOLPHIJN
IRENA CHAWRILSKA
JENNY HERMAN
RAÚL MATTA

Recipes

STARTERS

Green Pea Soup	08
Pulpo al Olivo	10
Stuffed Cabbage	12
“Fridge-Cleaner” Vegetable Stew	14

MAIN DISHES

Risotto with Codfish or Mushrooms	16
CONVIVIUM Bacalhau	18

DESSERTS

Shortcrust Apple Pie	20
Dutch Apple Pie	21
Rice Pudding	24
Smooth Fruit Salad	26

DRINK

Poncha	28
--------	----

Acknowledgements	30
------------------	----

Food Sustainably	32
------------------	----

Green Pea Soup

Green Pea Soup, or **erwtensoep**, is a hearty, thick soup typically enjoyed as a warm main dish during the cold winter months. Traditionally, it's served with **rookworst** (smoked sausage) and sometimes accompanied by slices of **ryebread** with **katenspek** (a special type of lard) and mustard spread on top. This comforting dish holds a special place in Dutch culture, particularly in connection with ice skating, as it was once sold from small food stalls at ice rinks. If the soup is allowed to sit for a day, its flavours intensify, and it is then known as **snert**. In fact, the weather during particularly harsh winters is often called **snertweer**, meaning weather for snert.

Ingredients

- 1 celeriac, peeled and cut into cubes
- 1 large potato, peeled and cut into cubes
- 300g dried green peas (soaked for a few hours)
- 4 medium carrots, peeled and chopped
- 3 leeks, cleaned and sliced
- 1.5L (about 6 cups) vegetable or meat stock
- Salt and freshly ground black pepper to taste
- Butter or oil for sautéing

OPTIONAL:

- Smoked sausage (rookworst)
- Rye bread with katenspek (lard) and mustard, for serving

Tip

The soup tastes even better the next day, as the flavours have time to develop. In fact, many people believe the taste of the soup improves after sitting overnight.

TEAM

RICK DOLPHIJN
CARMEN SOARES
MARTINHO SOARES
OVE JAKOBSEN
PAULA BARATA DIAS

Instructions

1. Prepare the Ingredients:

Heat a large pot over medium heat and add a bit of butter or oil. Once heated, add the diced potato and celeriac. Sauté for 3–5 minutes until lightly golden.

2. Add Vegetables and Stock:

Add the chopped carrots, leeks, and the soaked green peas to the pot. Pour in the stock, ensuring all the ingredients are covered. Season with a pinch of salt and pepper to taste. Bring the soup to a boil, then lower the heat and simmer for 30–40 minutes, or until the vegetables are tender and the peas have softened.

3. Blend the Soup:

Once the vegetables are fully cooked, use an immersion blender (or a regular blender in batches) to purée the soup until smooth and thick. The consistency should be creamy with a slight texture.

4. Final Touches:

Taste the soup and adjust the seasoning with more salt and pepper if needed. If a thinner consistency is desired, a little more stock or water.

5. Serve:

Ladle the soup into bowls and, if desired, serve with slices of smoked sausage, rye bread with katenspek, and mustard for an authentic Dutch experience.

Eet smakelijk!

(Enjoy your meal!)

Pulpo al Olivo

Pulpo al Olivo has been highly acclaimed in Peru since its creation in the 1980s. It is emblematic of what is known as Nikkei cuisine, a style fashioned over generations by cooks of Japanese ancestry living in Peru. What characterizes Nikkei cuisine is the combination of high-quality ingredients found in Peru and Japan's deep tradition of careful preparation of fish and seafood. The recipe below uses ingredients available at the Coimbra Municipal Market. A fusion of a fusion, it demonstrates that delicious renditions of iconic dishes are possible through adaption, openness, and teamwork.

Ingredients

- 6 egg yolks
- 100g yoghurt
- One big lemon
- Vegetable oil
- One fresh octopus
- 250g olives
- 6 cloves of garlic
- 3 celery branches
- 1 onion studded with 15-20 cloves (the spice)
- 2 tomatoes
- 3 avocados
- Old sandwich bread
- Salt and pepper to taste
- Mustard
- Parsley

TEAM

RAÚL MATTA
ANA TOMÁS
KATERINA ERIKSEN
NELSON FERREIRA

Instructions

Preparation:

- Gently tap and massage the fresh octopus for about five minutes, then place it into boiling water along with the tomatoes, celery branches, onion, parsley, and three garlic cloves. Let it cook for one hour.
- Prepare mayonnaise by mixing the egg yolks with the oil, a bit of mustard, and some lemon juice. Then, add the yoghurt to the mayonnaise. Once the mix is ready, transfer it to a blender, add the 250g of olives and three more garlic cloves, and blend until smooth.
- When the octopus is cooked, let it cool and slice it thinly.
- Cut the sandwich bread slices in half and toast them in the oven.
- Slice the avocados thinly.

Assembly:

Place the avocado slices on the toasted bread, the octopus slices over the avocado, and generously cover with the olive sauce.

And ready!

Stuffed Cabbage

Stuffed cabbage leaves with surplus wonders are the perfect leftover food recipe.

It is believed that cabbage rolls originated in Turkey, where it was common to wrap meat in vine leaves and fry it. This dish is said to have impressed the Swedish King Charles XII in the 18th century, who brought the recipe home to Sweden. From there, it reached Norway, and has been adapted to fit our commonplace ingredients. It is always advisable to honor the food by adding playfulness (*Homo ludens*), toying with the 5 tastes that humans can perceive: sour, salty, bitter, sweet, and umami.

Ingredients

You can fill cabbage rolls with any surplus food you have. The most important thing is to focus on the taste and texture of the filling.

TEAM

KATERINA ERIKSEN
ANNA VERMEHREN
OVE JAKOBSEN
VIVI STORSLETTEN

Instructions

Layer 1:

Roasted root vegetables (potatoes and sweet potato) in curry made from trimmings, along with apples for a sweet, strong taste.

Layer 2:

In this case, there were a lot of leftover mustard leaves with small yellow flowers. They were marinated with mustard and yoghurt.

Layer 3:

Aubergine skin, mushroom stems, and small red fruit and garlic skins were grilled for a smoky, slightly bitter, umami flavour.

The cabbage leaves were lightly boiled in salted water and then shocked in ice-cold water - then stuffed and baked in the oven for 10 minutes.

“Fridge-Cleaner” Vegetable Stew

This recipe is perfect to make before a new vegetable shopping trip, giving purpose to leftover ingredients from the past week that might otherwise be discarded.

Zero waste.

Ingredients

This recipe was created using ingredients donated by the local market. The box included ripe tomatoes, bell peppers, eggplants, zucchini, carrots, pointed cabbage, onions, potatoes, and leeks.

- 4 tomatoes
- 2 onions
- 2 carrots
- 3 potatoes
- 3 garlic cloves
- 2 red bell peppers
- 2 eggplants
- 2 zucchini
- 1 pointed cabbage
- 1 leek
- 4 eggs (1 per person)
- Salt and pepper to taste
- Aromatic herbs (thyme, parsley, bay leaf)
- 1dl olive oil
- 2dl white wine

TEAM

PAULA BARATA DIAS
KATERINA ERIKSEN

Instructions

- Dice the tomatoes, zucchini, potatoes, and eggplants into cubes.
- Slice the pointed cabbage into very thin strips.
- Chop the onions, leek, garlic, and bell peppers into slices.
- In a large pan, heat the olive oil with the herbs, then add the sliced onion, leek, and garlic. Sauté until golden.
- Add the diced vegetables and the bell peppers. Stir to prevent sticking. Once everything is well coated in olive oil, pour in the wine.
- Let it simmer on low heat for 15 minutes. Then, add 2dl of boiling water along with the pointed cabbage. Cook for another 10 minutes, then turn off the heat.
- Crack the eggs over the stew while hot, spacing them out so that each person receives a poached egg with their serving of vegetables and broth. Cover the pan with the lid while the eggs cook.
- To serve, place a slice of hard bread or pieces of dried bread at the bottom of each plate. Ladle the broth, egg, and vegetables over the bread.
- If you have any hard cheese in the fridge, grate some over each serving for extra flavour.

Eat while it's hot!

Risotto with Codfish or Mushrooms

Risotto, a creamy, comforting rice-based dish, offers infinite possibilities for adaptations and innovations. During the kick-off event, we wanted to prepare a version of risotto which took into consideration local products, sustainability, and Portuguese flavors. Instead of the typical arborio or carnaroli rice, we purchased a local variety of rice from the Coimbra Municipal Market. There, we also selected seasonal mushrooms, including hyper-local shiitakes (produced in Coimbra, just across the river by a small grower). For the vegetables, both for topping and for the broth base, we allowed ourselves to be led by what was in season. For the wine, again, we chose a local variety. Finally, for the cod and cheese, we used salted cod rather than fresh, and a semi-cured local cheese. The latter gave our dish an interesting sharpness that an Italian variety might have lacked. Our team members appreciated the exercise of choosing a dish that could be made more sustainable, fit for vegetarians, and a reflection of resourcefulness.

Ingredients

- Prepared salted cod fillets, or fresh cod fillets, if available
- Risotto rice (we used a local Portuguese variety, but Arborio, Carnaroli, or Vialone Nano work well)
- Yellow and red onion
- One head of garlic
- Carrots
- Leek
- Salt and pepper to taste
- Broccoli
- Lemon
- Mushrooms (choose your preferred variety – we used a mixture of brown champignon and shiitake)
- Dill, oregano, and thyme (fresh, if available)
- Butter
- Oil
- A semi-hard/cured cheese to blend into the risotto – we used a local Portuguese variety.
- Broth/stock (vegetable, fish, or meat-based, depending on preference)
- Dry white wine

TEAM

JENNY HERMAN

JONAS WALSTØE

PEDRO LEÓN

VIVI STORSLETTEN

Instructions

Risotto:

- Finely chop the onion, garlic, leek, and red onion. Sauté them in a pan with melted butter and a drizzle of oil over medium heat.
- Roughly chop the mushrooms and set them aside, with the exception of a small bowl – add these to the sautéing onion mixture and cook for several minutes.
- Add a bit more oil with the risotto rice, stirring and warming the mixture until the grains begin to turn opaque.
- Slightly reduce the heat and add a generous cup of wine, allowing it to slowly absorb into the rice mixture.
- Once the wine is nearly absorbed, begin adding the broth/stock gradually, stirring continuously.
- In a separate pan, sauté half of the reserved mushrooms in oil, salt, pepper, and herbs. Set aside. These will be mixed into the risotto when the broth is nearly absorbed to enhance the mushroom flavour.
- Squeeze the lemon juice into the risotto, and add the lemon remnants to the pot for extra depth of flavour.
- Continue adding broth/stock in small amounts, allowing the rice to absorb it gradually. Season with salt and pepper to taste. When the broth has just been absorbed, stir in the cheese, and serve with toppings (see below).

Preparing the Codfish & Vegetables:

- Soak the salted cod in water, then bring it just to a boil before removing it from the heat. Let it steep gently. If using fresh cod, you can choose to either bake or fry the fillets.
- Preheat the oven and oil a roasting pan. Chop the broccoli and carrots, toss them in oil, salt, and pepper, and bake until tender but still crisp.
- Pan-fry the remaining mushrooms in olive oil and butter until crispy and flavourful, seasoning with a pinch of salt.
- Melt some butter and mix in the herbs, then drizzle over the codfish before serving.

Serving:

Serve the risotto individually, allowing vegetarians to enjoy it with mushrooms and vegetables, while others can add the codfish and drizzle it with dill butter.

Enjoy your meal!

CONVIVIUM

Bacalhau

Codfish (Bacalhau) is treasured part of Portuguese Food Heritage, present in everyday life and an essential dish during Portuguese Christmas festivities. It pays homage to the cod fishing in the North Atlantic, a tradition practiced by the Portuguese since the Middle Ages. This codfish, sourced from Norwegian waters and dried and salted in the unique Portuguese way, is used to prepare this recipe – one of over a thousand Portuguese cod recipes. Like many others, it features simple ingredients such as onions, garlic, and potatoes. And, of course, the olive oil that defines Mediterranean culture.

Bringing together different products, cultures, and people in a truly convivial spirit, this is our CONVIVIUM Bacalhau!

Ingredients

(for 20 people)

- 10 codfish loins
- 20 medium-sized potatoes
- 5 onions
- 5 sliced garlic cloves
- 3dl extra virgin olive oil
- 2 laurel leaves
- 2 parsley sprigs
- 5 eggs
- Nutmeg
- Salt
- Pepper
- Grated bread
- Grated parmesan cheese

FOR BÉCHAMEL SAUCE:

- 1L milk
- 200gr flour*
- 250g butter
- Codfish cooking water

FOR TURNIP GREENS (GRELOS):

- 5 bunches of turnip sprouts
- 8 sliced garlic cloves
- 3dl extra virgin olive oil

*You can use corn starch to replace wheat flour for gluten intolerance; that was what we did

TEAM

MARIA JOSÉ ARAÚJO

CLAUDETE MOREIRA

FERNANDO GARCIA-DORY

RUI LOBO

VIRGINIE AMILIEN

Instructions

Codfish:

- Put the cod in a pan with water, bring it to a boil, then reduce the heat to the minimum, and let it cook for 20 minutes. Remove from the heat and shred the cod.
- Meanwhile, wash and peel the potatoes, then boil them for about 20 minutes. Once cooked, remove them from the water and mash with a fork.
- Chop the onions and garlic, add the laurel and the olive oil, and braise them.
- Add the shredded codfish to the pan and let it braise. Then, add the mashed potatoes and the chopped parsley, mixing thoroughly.
- Season with salt and pepper to taste.
- Add all five eggs and mix again until well combined.

Béchamel sauce:

- Melt butter in a large saucepan over medium heat. Add flour and whisk into the melted butter until smooth. Cook and stir about 4 minutes.
- Increase the heat and slowly whisk in the milk and codfish cooking water until the mixture thickens.
- Reduce the heat to medium-low, then add salt, pepper, and nutmeg. Continue to cook for about 10 minutes.

Assembly:

- On an oven-safe serving plate, spread the cod and potato mixture. Cover with the béchamel sauce and sprinkle with the grated bread and parmesan.
- Place it in the oven and bake until golden brown. Leave some space on the plate for adding the sautéed turnip leaves at the end.

Sautéed Turnip Greens (Grelós):

- Wash the turnip leaves very well. Add salt and boil them for 5 minutes, then drain thoroughly.
- In a frying pan, heat a generous amount of olive oil and sauté the chopped garlic.
- Add the boiled turnip leaves, mix with the garlic, and sauté.
- Serve the leaves next to the codfish when done.

Shortcrust Apple Pie

The apple pie traditions of three countries, each with subtle distinctions, were merged by this dessert group. Polish pies often feature steamed apples with added pears and apricots in a thin, elegant crust. German variations frequently include a topping of vanilla-enriched whipped cream.

Dutch Apple Pie

The Dutch are known for their thick-rimmed apple pie, which often includes raisins.

The story of the apple pie we all know and love today begins in England, but its origins can actually be traced to the far-reaching lands of the Ottoman Empire.

It should come as no surprise that—regardless of the origin of the apple pie—it is best served when it comes fresh out of the oven.

SHORT CRUSTED APPLE PIE

Ingredients

(Recipe for 4-6 people)

BASE:

- Mould with a diameter of 28cm
- Dough: 300g flour
- 200g butter
- 50g sugar
- 1 egg

FILLING:

- About 1.5kg apples
- 1 teaspoon cinnamon
- 100g brown sugar
- Pinch of cardamom
- 1-2 tablespoons breadcrumbs

TEAM

IRENA CHAWRILSKA
ANNA VERMEHREN
ELLEN ZOETE
JOÃO PEDRO GOMES
JOSEFINA SALVADO

Instructions

- Mix the flour, butter, sugar, and egg well, then knead the dough. Form a ball, cover with a linen cloth, and leave in the fridge for at least 30 minutes.
- Wash and peel the apples, then dice them. In a hot frying pan, melt the sugar and cinnamon. Add the diced apples and cardamom. Cook until the apples are browned, about 15-18 minutes.
- Roll out 3/4 of the chilled dough on a linen napkin or baking paper. Using the napkin or paper, flip the dough and line a greased baking tin. Prick the bottom with a fork, sprinkle with breadcrumbs, and place the fried apples on top.
- Roll out the remaining dough and cut it into strips. Arrange the strips on top of the apples to form a lattice pattern. Fold the sides of the pastry together.
- Bake in a preheated oven at 200°C for about 35 minutes.
- Dust with icing sugar before serving.

DUTCH APPLE PIE

Ingredients

- 450g flour
- 225g sugar
- 250g cold butter
- 2 eggs
- 1kg sour apples (e.g. Golden Reinette apples)
- 50g sugar
- 3 teaspoons cinnamon
- 100g raisins
- Salt
- Lemon juice

TEAM

ELLEN ZOETE
ANNA VERMEHREN
IRENA CHAWRILSKA
JOÃO PEDRO GOMES
JOSEFINA SALVADO

Instructions

- Put the raisins in a bowl of warm water and let them soak for a while.
- Preheat the oven to 175°C with top and bottom heat.
- Beat the 2 eggs in a small bowl.
- Mix the flour, butter, sugar, a good pinch of salt, and about 1.5 eggs (reserve the rest of the egg for brushing the pie) together form a smooth, compact dough.
- Line a springform pan with baking paper and grease it.
- Take about 3/4 of the dough and spread it over the bottom and sides of the springform pan. You can either roll out the dough and fit it into the pan, or for an easier method, press the dough directly into the bottom of the pan with your fingers. Make sure the pan is evenly covered with dough.
- Peel and chop the apples into small pieces. Place them in a bowl and drizzle with lemon juice. Drain the raisins and mix them with the apples, along with the sugar and cinnamon.
- Fill the pie crust with the apple mixture.
- Roll out the remaining dough and cut into long strips. Arrange them in a diamond pattern over the apple pie, pressing the edges down.
- Brush the top of the pie with the rest of the egg.
- Bake in the preheated oven for about 1 hour, or until the pie turns a nice golden brown.

Enjoy it with whipped cream
or vanilla ice-cream!

Rice Pudding

Rice Pudding is a combination of two similar dessert recipes from two different countries. **Arroz Doce** is a Portuguese dessert made by cooking rice and then creaming it with milk, sugar, and egg yolks. It is typically served with cinnamon on top. **Risikrem** is a Norwegian rice pudding made from rice porridge and whipped cream, topped with a red berry sauce. We used the preparation of the first and added the topping of the latter, but with a twist: **orange cream**.

Ingredients

(For 30 people)

RICE:

- 6L water
- 1kg carolino rice
- 1 tablespoon salt
- 6L milk
- 5 cinnamon sticks
- Peel of 2 medium-sized lemons
- 18 egg yolks
- 150g corn starch

ORANGE CREAM:

- 2L fresh orange juice
- 3 sticks of cinnamon
- 8 cloves
- 400g sugar
- 240ml water
- 150g corn starch

OPTIONAL:

- Before making the orange juice, zest some oranges to use for topping.

TEAM

SÉRGIO REBELO
ATLE WEHN HEGNES
EULÁLIA MARQUES
ILDEFONSO MORENO

Instructions

RICE:

- In a large pan, bring the water to a boil. Add the rice and cook until the water evaporates almost completely.
- In another pan, heat the milk, cinnamon, and lemon peels. Let it boil.
- Add the milk mixture to the rice, stirring well. Let it cook, mixing it occasionally, until it becomes creamy.
- Add the sugar, and mix well.
- Whisk the egg yolks. Take about a cup of the rice mixture to a bowl and add the corn starch.
- Stir this new mixture into the egg yolks to prevent them from cooking.
- Add the egg yolk mixture to the rice, stirring well. Keep mixing until it thickens.
- Once ready, divide the rice into bowls or pour it into a tray.

ORANGE CREAM:

- In a pan, bring the orange juice, cloves, and cinnamon to a boil.
- Add the sugar and stir until it dissolves.
- In a small bowl, dissolve the corn starch with a few spoons of the orange mixture.
- Reduce the heat of the pan, then slowly add the corn starch mixture to the orange juice, stirring it constantly.
- Let it cook for about 5 minutes or until it thickens, stirring continuously.
- Remove from heat and let it cool.

ASSEMBLY:

- Once both the rice and orange cream have cooled, pour a few spoons of the orange cream on top of the rice pudding, and finish with a sprinkle of orange zest.

Smooth Fruit Salad

This is a way to use fruit in an advanced stage of ripeness, which would normally be unfit for eating raw.

The selection of fruits should depend on availability.

By incorporating a purée made from the ripest, juiciest fruits, this dessert gains a unique texture and becomes more visually appealing.

This recipe was created using only fruit discarded by vendors at the local market.

We present it as an example of how to combat food waste and promote food sustainability!

Ingredients

- Banana
- Orange
- Apple
- Mango
- Strawberries
- Pear
- Papaya
- Kiwi
- Water

Instructions

- Wash the pieces of fruit thoroughly. Remove any inedible skin as well as any rotten parts.
- Dice the fruit into cubes and place them in the serving bowl.
- Select the juiciest fruit pieces (in our case: strawberry, orange, pear, and apple bits) and place them in a blender. Add water as needed until you obtain a smooth purée.
- Pour the fruit purée over the diced fruit and serve as is.

Thus, waste becomes a tasty,
beautiful dessert!

TEAM

CARMEN SOARES
ANA TOMÁS

Poncha

Poncha is a traditional drink from Madeira Island. It is made with aguardente de cana-de-açúcar (distilled alcohol from sugar cane juice), honey or sugar, and traditionally either orange juice, lemon juice, or both! This is a recipe for Poncha Regional.

Ingredients

- 750ml sugar cane aguardente
- 450ml fresh orange juice
- 350ml fresh lemon juice
- 50ml cold water
- Honey

TEAM

EULÁLIA MARQUES
ATLE WEHN HEGNES
ILDEFONSO MORENO
MARTINHO SOARES

Instructions

- Before juicing the fruits, peel two oranges and two lemons. Cut half of an orange and one lemon into small pieces. Place them in a jug and use a long, round wooden kitchen utensil – known colloquially in Madeira as a “caralinho” – to muddle them thoroughly until a foam starts to form.
- Add the alcohol, fruit juices, and the water, mixing well.
- Gradually add the honey, stirring continuously so it does not become too sweet. Keep mixing until a layer of foam forms on top.

Acknowledgements

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Director:
José Luís Marques

Names from right to left ↓

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Rodrigo Pires
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Food Sustainability

Origin of products

*"Undetermined" refers to products that don't indicate their origin on the packaging. This category includes almost all spices and sugar, which typically only mention being packaged in Portugal, despite clearly not being of Portuguese origin.

Waste

Organic - 25,20kg

Plastic - 2,50kg

Post-meal food waste - 5kg

Food Donated to ReFood

20L of soup

7kg of food

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RECIPE Book

